

IMPLEMENTATION OF REMOTE WORK POLICY IN THE ICT INDUSTRY

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Abstract:

This research looks at how demographic factors affect the way telework laws are implemented in the ICT industry. Data from 161 analyses of the replies were conducted to ascertain the effects of telework on work hours, workplace productivity and performance, and accessibility to a healthy work-life balance. The results demonstrate that telework has a positive impact on work, better performance and production, as well as life balance. Nevertheless, there were problems with hours of labor and availability. Even though younger workers frequently benefited more from telework, factors such as sex, marital status, and work-life balance were not significantly influenced by education or wealth outcomes. The report highlights the need for tailored strategies to improve telework laws and meet the particular needs of different ICT industry employee associations.

Keywords: Implementation of remote work policy, ICT Industry, work-life balance, performance and productivity, work hours and availability

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

The rapid migration to digital-first has forced every industry sector on a journey towards radical redesign in operational models. Information and communications technology (ICT) is also an area that is heavily featured in the small and medium enterprise sector. Telework has created opportunities and challenges for these businesses (Brynjolfsson, E., & McAfee, A., 2014).

ICT SMEs must herald stringent telework policies for various reasons, including the current scenario. COVID-19 triggered most organizations to operate remotely without any plan, showing all loopholes in existing policies and infra. Furthermore, there has been an increase in the number of employees who seek a flexible way to work — thanks to technology making remote working more possible (Bloom, N. et al., 2015).

As a result, ICT SMEs face the TWO-PRONGED thrust of benefitting from telework advantages and curtailing risks to productivity, lower staff morale, and potential data loss. For several reasons, it is essential to grasp the details of implementing successful telework policies in the ICT sector (International Labour Organization, 2020). For one, they can offer significant benefits when optimizing remote work arrangements and postures for increased employee satisfaction and organizational performance. Second, this research may also help to establish a best practice and support system relating to challenges with telework for ICT SMEs. Finally, the results of this study provide valuable insights that could guide policymakers and industry stakeholders in adopting appropriate policies to promote telework adoption (Hall, S., & Soskice, D., 2001).

This study aims to determine the components that ensure that telework policies have been successfully implemented in ICT SMEs. It will examine the issues these businesses face, the remedies utilized to solve them, and the impact of Telework on Work-life Balance, employee well-being, and corporate performance. By exploring these topics, this research aims to present recommendations for improving telework practices and a thorough knowledge of the telework landscape within the ICT SME sector.

Current State of Knowledge

The workers use video conferences, email, Line, and cell phones to connect to a remote computer site while working from home. To improve work-life balance, flexible work arrangements entail changing working hours and locations (Songsanyos, P. & Iamamporn, S. (2022)). Employees may work from anywhere with this flexible schedule, including their homes or the company's main office. Employees who work remotely may benefit from lower commuting costs, a better work-life balance, and professional advancement. The benefits to the firm include higher staff satisfaction and retention, better productivity, and cost savings on physical resources (Ghoshi, B. 2022).

Nakrošienė, Bučiūnienė, and Goštautaitė (2019) suggest that Regulations allowing for remote work provide employees with a sense of autonomy. A balance between the liberty offered by remote work and the worry over potentially excessive work demands is highlighted by the fact that these policies can sometimes make people feel as though they are being forced to work unreasonably long hours. Lippe and Lippenyi (2020) suggest that the findings indicate that remote work improves employee enthusiasm and productivity by enabling a better work-life balance. Age significantly impacts how remote work regulations about work-life balance are implemented in the ICT industry. Compared to older employees, younger employees believe that remote work regulations offer an outstanding work-life balance.

Implementation of Remote Work Policy in the ICT Industry. The traditional lines separating work and life have drastically altered in China due to working remotely. Chinese laborers have traditionally been a part of a "996" culture. It stipulates that work must begin at nine in the morning, starting at 6 p.m. and up until nine p.m. every day. The remote work paradigm allows for greater flexibility and helps workers manage their home and professional lives (Zhou, D., 2024).

Based on Bick R. et al. (2020), empathy is vital for fostering connections, inclusivity, and community without face-to-face engagement. Encouraging more one-on-one catchups and social contacts among team members may avert loneliness and demotivation by creating an atmosphere where people can easily voice their thoughts and ideas. Wei, L. and Z. Yun said that norms for remote work will be implemented by China's ICT industry by 2021. There would need to be clear guidelines about personnel availability and work hours to maintain high productivity. It may be possible to reduce the stress associated with working remotely, such as decreased team cohesion and communication barriers, by setting precise work schedules and ensuring employees are available during these hours. Schedule frequent check-in periods and promote virtual meetings to lessen the impacts of isolation and preserve team engagement and connectedness.

Working remotely may increase productivity by removing commuting and providing greater employment flexibility, there are some issues with teamwork and communication. The ICT sector's regulations around remote work has significantly altered employee availability and work hours, frequently muddying the lines between work and personal time. Due to its flexible nature, remote work might result in longer work hours because of greater accessibility, which may cause problems with personal and professional obligations. In remote work environments, the expectation of availability can exacerbate stress-associated with the job and affect productivity and overall job satisfaction (Errichiello, L. & Pianese, T. 2021).

Implementation of Remote Work Policy in the ICT Industry. To investigate work-family interference from three perspectives—work-daily, work-work, and work-study—an analytical framework known as "assemblages of work-family interference" is put forward. Benefits of work-from-home policies include reduced commuting times, fewer workplace distractions, more job autonomy, flexibility in working hours, and improved work-life integration (Sun et al.; W., 2022). Enhancing the ability of employees to manage themselves is necessary; the business must assist them in doing so. Organizations may greatly benefit from successful self-management as it can improve work habits and increase learning, performance, job satisfaction, and success (Xing C. et al., 2024).

Theoretical Underpinnings

Social exchange theory offers strong foundation for comprehending the dynamics of telework policy implementation in ICT SMEs. According to this idea, people choose their relationships based on a cost-benefit analysis to minimize expenses and increase rewards (Kelley & Thibaut, 1959). Employees who telecommute assess the advantages of flexibility and independence against possible disadvantages like decreased social connection and isolation. In a similar vein, businesses weigh the benefits of lower expenses and higher output against the difficulties of overseeing remote workers and preserving company culture.

This theory may be used to examine the elements that influence employee acceptance of telework rules, the impact of telework on organizational performance, and the importance of trust and communication in its implementation. By investigating tele work's perceived costs and advantages for individuals and businesses, this study can offer insight into the underlying factors driving the acceptance and efficacy of remote work arrangements in the ICT industry. Employers and workers participate in social transactions while working remotely; workers offer their expertise and time in return for advantages like flexibility, work-life balance, and job satisfaction. On the

other hand, companies provide remote work options in return for more output, lower costs, and better staff retention. This theoretical framework enables an analysis of remote employment's perceived costs and advantages for individuals and companies. It also aids in identifying variables that impact the successful implementation of telework policies, such as trust, communication, and company culture.

Objectives

This study aimed to determine the extent of implementing the remote work policy in the ICT industry during the Third quarter of 2024. Specifically, the study seeks to answer the following questions: 1) the profile of the respondents according to the variable age, sex, civil status, higher educational attainment, average family monthly income; 2) the extent of implementing the remote work policy in the ICT industry according to the area of work-life balance, performance and productivity, work hours and availability; and 3) significant difference in the extent of implementing the remote work policy in the ICT industry when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

Methodology

This section presents a discussion of the research methodology used, the subjects and respondents of the study, the research instruments used, the validity and reliability of the instruments, the procedure for data gathering, and the statistical tools and procedures for data analysis.

Research Design

This study used a descriptive research approach to investigate the amount of remote work policy implementation in the ICT industry during the third quarter of 2024. As Creswell (2014) stated, this method is appropriate for investigating and explaining events as they occur spontaneously. Using descriptive research, this study aims to provide a comprehensive account of remote work practices in the ICT industry, contributing to a better understanding of the industry's transition to remote work arrangements. Considering the nature of the data involved, the descriptive research design was used in this study. According to McCombes (2020), descriptive research consists of describing, recording, analyzing, and interpreting phenomena' present nature, composition, or processes that focus on prevailing conditions or how a person aims to represent a population, situation, or phenomenon accurately and systematically.

Study Respondents

A stratified random selection technique will be used to choose the one hundred sixty-one (161) research participants, ensuring representativeness across a range of work activities. With 60 employees in administration and 101 in manufacturing, the sample will be drawn equitably from the production and administrative divisions. To provide a solid basis for analyzing the organization's execution of its remote work policy, this sampling technique aims to collect the various experiences and opinions of employees within these crucial departments.

Instruments

The study used a self-made survey questionnaire. It was subjected to validity (4.74-excellent) and reliability (0.776-acceptable). All of them were interpreted as worthy and good; respectively. The self-made survey questionnaire with two (2) components will be used to collect data for this study. Information on the respondents' profile, including age, sex, marital status, the greatest level of education attained, and the average monthly family income will be gathered in Part 1. Part II of the questionnaire shall determine the extent of implementing the remote work policy in the ICT industry according to the following areas: Work-life balance, Performance and productivity, and Work hours and availability. It consists of seven (7) line-item questions per area. The scores about the degree of implementation of the remote work policy will be tallied and evaluated on a 5-point rating system, where 5 represents "Always," 4 represents "Often," 3 represents "Sometimes," 2 represents "Rarely," and 1 represents "Not at All."

Data Gathering Procedure

This study was obtained through a survey questionnaire. A questionnaire is a written instrument containing a series of questions designed to collect information from respondents (Babbie, 2016). After determining validity and reliability, the researcher wrote a letter of permission to conduct the study. After approval, the researcher set the data collection schedule and the letter's requirements. In the study, the researcher personally described the goal, gave the questionnaire to the participants to help them fill it out and provide the necessary information, and then collected the surveys. The respondents received assurances that the data collected would be kept private. After

answering the survey, the questionnaires were immediately retrieved, and the data were tallied, analyzed, and interpreted by the researcher to solve the problem with answers and come up with a valid conclusion. The encoded data was then processed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No. 1 employs the descriptive-analytical scheme and frequency and percentage distributions to determine the respondents' profile regarding the selected variables: age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, and average monthly income.

Objective No. 2 employs the descriptive-analytical scheme and mean to determine the extent of implementing the remote work policy in the ICT industry according to work-life balance, performance and productivity, and Work hours and availability.

Objective No. 3 also employs the comparative-analytical scheme and Mann-Whitney U test to determine the extent of implementing the remote work policy in the ICT industry when grouped according to the aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 4 used the comparative-analytical scheme and Mann-Whitney U test to determine whether or not a significant difference exists in the extent of implementing the remote work policy in the ICT industry when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

Ethical Consideration

The concepts that direct the study designs and procedures are known as ethical concerns in research. There is a code of behavior that scientists and researchers must always follow while gathering information from individuals (P. Bhandari, 2022). Voluntary participation, informed permission, privacy, and plagiarism will all be severely enforced. Participants in the study will not be coerced or under any duress, they are free to leave at any moment and not provide a justification for doing so. The goal and design of the study, together with its advantages, disadvantages, and repercussions, will all be fully disclosed to the research participants. The confidentiality of any information on their personal information or any other type of identifying information about them will be guaranteed to the research participants.

Results and Discussion

This section presents, analyzes, and interprets the data that were gathered consistent with its predetermined objectives.

Table 1
Profile of the Respondents

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Age	Younger (less than 31 years old)	97	60.2
	Older (31 years and above)	64	39.8
	Total	161	100
Sex	Male	110	68.30
	Female	51	31.70
	Total	161	100
Civil Status	Single	80	49.7
	Married	81	50.3
	Total	161	100
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower (College Level)	120	74.5
	Higher (Post Grad Level)	41	25.5
	Total	161	100
Average Family Monthly	Lower (less than 11,000)	67	41.6

Income	Higher (11,000 and above)	94	58.4
	Total	161	100

Table 1 shows that out of 161 respondents, 97 (60.2%) belong to the younger category, while 64 (39.8%) belong to the older category. On sex, 110 respondents (68.30%) belong to the male category, while 51 respondents (31.70%) belong to the female category. Regarding civil status, 80 respondents (49.7%) belong to the single category, while 81 (50.3%) belong to the married category. On the other hand, the highest educational attainment, 120 respondents (74.5%), belongs to the lower category, while 41 respondents (25.5%) belong to the highest category. On average family monthly income, 67 respondents (41.6%) belong to the lower category, while 94 (58.4%) belong to the higher category.

It reveals that the young are mainly male and evenly split between single and married individuals. Most respondents have a college-level education and fall into the higher income bracket.

Table 2

Extent of Implementing the Remote Work Policy in the ICT Industry in the Area Work-life Balance

Area		
A. Work-life balance	Mean	Interpretation
1. I can flexibly arrange my work schedule under the remote work policy, allowing me to balance work and life better.	4.79	Very Great Extent
2. Remote work enables me to manage my work time more effectively, thus giving me more personal life space.	4.61	Very Great Extent
3. Remote work helps me find it easier to balance family and work, achieving a better work-life balance.	4.81	Very Great Extent
4. Remote work allows for a better balance between family and work, improving work-life balance.	4.81	Very Great Extent
5. Remote work induces more significant work pressure, making it difficult to handle family matters or personal life effectively.	2.90	Moderate Extent
6. Despite the flexibility provided by remote work, I often need to work overtime or deal with work matters, negatively affecting my involvement in family and personal life. In addition, I have been able to work in the field of education and training for my family and personal life.	2.95	Moderate Extent
7. The remote work policy does not significantly contribute to maintaining a balance between work and life, and there is a relatively poor balance between work and personal life. I feel there is a relatively poor balance between work and personal life.	2.48	Low Extent
Overall Mean	3.91	Great Extent

Table 2 shows the extent of the implementation of the remote work policy in the ICT industry regarding work-life balance. The overall mean is 3.91, interpreted as "great extent." The highest mean is 4.81, interpreted as "very great extent" on item no. 3, "Remote work helps me find it easier to balance family and work, achieving a better work-life balance," and no. 4, "Remote work allows for a better balance between family and work, improving work-life balance." The lowest mean is 2.48, interpreted as "low extent," on item no. 7 "The remote work policy does not significantly contribute to maintaining a balance between work and life, and I feel there is a relatively poor balance between work and personal life. I feel there is a relatively poor balance between work and personal life".

The result implies that the remote work policy does not significantly contribute to balancing work and life. Under the remote work policy, it will give some employees a relatively poor balance between their work and personal lives.

The result confirms in the study of Allen (2012) that work-life balance is generally considered an individual-level concept that equates to a lack of conflict or incompatibility between workers' families and work roles.

Table 3

Extent of Implementing the Remote Work Policy in the ICT Industry in the Area of Performance and Productivity

Area		
B. Collaboration between Education Providers	Mean	Interpretation
1. The remote work policy enables me to manage my work time more effectively, improving my work performance.	4.55	Very Great Extent
2. In the remote work environment, I can concentrate more, leading to increased work efficiency.	4.59	Very Great Extent
3. Although I sometimes work from home, my performance is not	4.41	Great Extent

significantly affected.

4. Remote work allows me to balance work and life better, enhancing my enthusiasm and productivity.	3.61	Great Extent
5. While I can work from home, the lack of an office atmosphere may sometimes affect my performance.	3.81	Great Extent
6. The remote work policy does not significantly improve my work performance and productivity and may even sometimes reduce my efficiency.	3.65	Great Extent
7. Remote work enhances my ability to collaborate effectively, improving overall team productivity	3.89	Great Extent
Overall Mean	4.08	Great Extent

Table 3 shows the extent of the implementation of the remote work policy in the ICT industry in terms of performance and productivity. The overall mean is 4.08, interpreted as "great extent." The highest mean is 4.59, interpreted as "very great extent" on item no. 2: "In the remote work environment, I can concentrate more, increasing work efficiency." The lowest mean is 3.61, interpreted as "great extent" on item no. 4: "Remote work allows me to balance work and life better, enhancing my enthusiasm and productivity."

The result implies that remote work allows for a better balance between work and life, enhancing enthusiasm and productivity. While employees see some benefits in work-life balance and productivity, this area has the lowest perceived impact compared to other factors.

Lippe & Lippenyi (2020) claim that remote work boosts passion and productivity by enabling workers to better combine their personal and professional lives. Even while work-life balance and productivity are positively impacted by remote work, these benefits are thought to be less significant than other advantages.

Table 4

Extent of Implementing the Remote Work Policy in the ICT Industry in the Area Work Hours and Availability

Area	Mean	Interpretation
C. Relevance of Courses		
1. Under the remote work policy, I can arrange my work hours more flexibly, allowing me to provide more work hours when needed.	4.44	Great Extent
2. Although I can work from home, my work hours and availability have stayed the same.	3.72	Great Extent
3. Remote work enables me to work during non-traditional work hours, increasing my work hours and availability.	4.48	Great Extent
4. While I can choose my work hours, sometimes balancing work and personal time is challenging.	3.84	Great Extent
5. Work hours and availability are more respected and recognized under remote work circumstances.	4.35	Great Extent
6. The remote work policy makes me feel more liberated, but sometimes, it makes me think I am expected to work unreasonable hours.	3.47	Moderate Extent
7. The remote work policy has mostly stayed the same in my work hours and availability; I still face similar work-hour pressures and availability demands.	4.37	Great Extent
Overall Mean	4.10	Great Extent

Table 4 shows the extent of the implementation of the remote work policy in the ICT industry regarding work hours and availability. The overall mean is 4.10, interpreted as "great extent." The highest mean is 4.48, interpreted as "great extent," on item no.3, "Remote work enables me to work during non-traditional work hours, increasing my work hours and availability," while the lowest mean is 3.47, interpreted as "moderate extent," is on item no. 6 "The remote work policy makes me feel more liberated, but sometimes, it makes me think I am expected to work unreasonable hours." According to the result, employees may feel freer when working remotely, but they may also feel under pressure to put in excessively long hours. It provides the flexibility that comes with working remotely, but worries about maybe too much work are present.

The finding confirms what Nakrošienė, Bučiūnienė, and Goštautaitė (2019) found, which is that rules allowing remote work provide workers with a sense of independence. A balance between the liberty offered by remote work and the worry over potentially excessive work demands is highlighted by the fact that these policies can sometimes make people feel as though they are being forced to work unreasonably long hours.

Table 5

Difference in the Extent of Implementing the Remote Work Policy in the ICT Industry in the Area of Work-life Balance when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	97	88.44	2382.500	0.010	0.05	Significant
	Older	64	69.73				
Sex	Male	110	76.30	2288.500	0.053	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	51	91.13				
Civil Status	Single	80	78.98	3078.000	0.572	0.05	Not Significant
	Married	81	83.00				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	120	80.56	2407.500	0.834	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	41	82.28				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	67	84.53	2912.500	0.403	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	94	78.48				

Table 5 shows the difference in the extent of implementing the remote work policy in the ICT Industry regarding work-life balance.

On age, the mean rank score for the younger category is 88.44 with a p-value of 0.010, which is less than the level of significance of 0.05, while the older category is 69.73, with a p-value of 0.010, which is less than the level of significance of 0.05, interpreted as significant.

On sex, the mean rank score for the male category is 76.30 with a p-value of 0.053, which is greater than the significance level of 0.05, while the female category is 91.13 with a p-value of 0.053, which is greater than the level of significance of 0.05, interpreted as not significant.

On civil status, the mean rank score for the single category is 78.98 with a p-value of 0.572, which is greater than the level of significance of 0.05, while the married category is 83.00 with a p-value of 0.572, interpreted as not significant.

On highest educational attainment, the mean rank score for the lower category is 80.56 with a p-value of 0.834, which is greater than the level of significance of 0.05, while the higher category is 82.28 with a p-value of 0.834, which is greater than the level of relevance interpreted as not significant.

On average family monthly income, the mean rank score for lower is 84.53 with a p-value of 0.403, which is greater than the level of significance of 0.05, while the higher category is 78.48 with a p-value of 0.403, which is greater than the level of significance of 0.05, interpreted as not significant.

The findings suggest that age significantly impacts how far the ICT sector implements remote work policies to maintain work-life balance. In light of the remote work policy, younger employees view a higher work-life balance than older employees.

Lippe and Lippenyi (2020) suggest that the findings indicate that remote work improves employee enthusiasm and productivity by enabling a better work-life balance. Age significantly impacts how remote work regulations about work-life balance are implemented in the ICT industry. Compared to older employees, younger employees believe that remote work regulations offer an outstanding work-life balance.

Table 6

Difference in the Extent of Implementing the Remote Work Policy in the ICT Industry in the Area of Performance and Productivity when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	97	95.65	1683.000	0.000	0.05	Significant
	Older	64	58.80				
Sex	Male	110	72.84	1907.000	0.001	0.05	Significant

		Female	51	98.61			
Civil Status		Single	80	98.14	1868.500	0.000	Significant
		Married	81	64.07			
Highest Educational Attainment		Lower	120	88.58	1550.000	0.000	Significant
		Higher	41	58.80			
Average Family Monthly Income		Lower	67	102.02	1740.500	0.000	Significant
		Higher	94	66.02			

Table 6 shows the difference in the extent of implementing the remote work policy in the ICT industry regarding performance and productivity.

On age, the mean rank score for the younger category is 95.65 with a p-value of 0.000, which is less than the level of significance of 0.05, while the older category is 58.80 with a p-value of 0.000, which is less than the level of significance of 0.05, interpreted as a significant.

On sex, the mean rank score for the male category is 72.84 with a p-value of 0.001, which is less than the level of significance of 0.05, while the female category is 98.61 with a p-value of 0.001, which is less than the level of significance of 0.05, interpreted as significant.

On civil status, the mean rank score for the single category is 98.14 with a p-value of 0.000, which is less than the level of significance of 0.05, while the married category is 64.07 with a p-value of 0.000, which is less than the level of significance of 0.05, interpreted as a significant.

On highest educational attainment, the mean rank score for the lower category is 88.58 with a p-value of 0.000, which is less than the level of significance of 0.05, while the higher category is 58.80 with a p-value of 0.000, which is less than the level of significance of 0.05, interpreted as significant.

On average family monthly income, the mean rank score for the lower category is 102.02 with a p-value of 0.000, which is less than the significance level of 0.05, while the higher category is 66.02 with a p-value of 0.000, which is less than the level of significance of 0.05, interpreted as significant.

The result implies that all the examined variables—age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, and average family monthly income—significantly affect the extent of implementing the remote work policy in the ICT industry in terms of performance and productivity. Younger employees, females, singles, those with lower educational attainment, and those with lower average family monthly income perceive excellent performance and productivity improvement under the remote work policy.

The outcome supports Vandello, B.'s results. as well as Van, H. (2013), which found that demographic parameters such as age, gender, marital status, income level, and education level highly influence remote work rules' impact on productivity and performance.

According to the survey, those who are younger, female, unmarried, have less education and make less money on a monthly average for their family all feel that performance and productivity have increased more when working remotely.

Table 7

Difference in the Extent of Implementing the Remote Work Policy in the ICT Industry in the Area of Work Hours and Availability when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	97	84.25	2789.000	0.270		Not Significant
	Older	64	76.08				
Sex	Male	110	86.15	2239.000	0.037	0.05	Significant
	Female	51	69.90				
Civil Status	Single	80	78.66	3052.500	0.520		Not Significant
	Married	81	83.31				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	120	75.98	1857.000	0.018		Significant

Attainment	Higher	41	95.71			
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	67	77.72	2929.500	0.445	Not Significant
	Higher	94	83.34			

Table 7 shows the difference in the extent of implementing of the remote work policy in the ICT industry regarding work hours and availability.

On age, the mean rank score for the younger category is 84.25, with a p-value of 0.270, greater than the significance level of 0.05, while the older category is 76.08, with a p-value of 0.270, greater than 0.05, interpreted as insignificant.

On sex, the mean rank score for the male category is 86.15, with a p-value of 0.037, which is less than the significance level of 0.05, while the female category is 69.90, with a p-value of 0.037, which is less than 0.05, interpreted as significant.

On civil status, the mean rank score for the single category is 78.66 with a p-value of 0.520, which is greater than the significance level of 0.05, while the married category is 83.31 with a p-value of 0.520, which is greater than the level of significance of 0.05, interpreted as not significant.

On highest educational attainment, the mean rank score for the lower category is 75.98 with a p-value of 0.018, which is less than the level of significance of 0.05, while the higher category is 95.71 with a p-value of 0.018, which is less than the level of significance of 0.05, interpreted as significant.

On average family monthly income, the mean rank score for the lower category is 77.72 with a p-value of 0.445, which is greater than the significance level of 0.05, while the higher category is 83.34, with a p-value of 0.445, which is greater than the level of significance of 0.05, interpreted as not significant.

The findings suggest that the degree to which the ICT industry implements remote work policies concerning work hours and availability is mainly influenced by factors related to sex and the highest level of education. More specifically, men and those with higher levels of education feel that the remote work policy significantly influences their availability and working hours.

The outcome is consistent with Chung and Lippe, V.D. (2020), who found that opinions on remote work policies in the ICT sector are highly influenced by factors such as gender and educational achievement. It showed that when it came to working remotely, men and those with greater levels of education reported a greater influence on them work hours and availability.

Conclusions

The results indicate that work-life balance, performance, and productivity have all benefited from the substantial implementation of remote work policies in the ICT sector. Remote work offers flexibility and autonomy, which is valued by employees and improves workplace satisfaction and productivity. Nonetheless, issues with managing work hours. Furthermore, possible burnout needs to be addressed. Other demographic characteristics, such as sex, civil status, education. Moreover, income did not significantly differ from each other, although demographic factors like age did impact views of work-life balance, performance, and productivity. The study's conclusions led to the following recommendations suggested: 1) Optimize Work-Life Balance: Businesses should keep putting work-life balance efforts at the top of their priority list. To do this, they should establish limits, encourage frequent breaks, and provide clear instructions for remote work arrangements; 2) To improve performance management, create measures for performance reviews that are compatible with remote work settings and give staff members regular feedback; 3) Work Hours and Availability: Put mechanisms in place to avoid burnout, such as establishing precise guidelines for working hours, promoting time management techniques, and making mental health resources available; 4) Tailored Approaches: To meet the requirements and problems of various age groups, consider putting age-specific programs in place; 5) Continuous Evaluation: Evaluate remote work policies on a routine basis to see how effective they are and adapt as needed in response to employee input and evolving work environments.

By putting these suggestions into practice, businesses may reduce potential barriers, preserve a positive work atmosphere and enhance employee well-being while reaping the benefits of remote work.

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